

Table S1. Trend of giant clam population density in Palawan from 1984-2019 extracted from six published papers, 13 reports, five theses, and data from the recent survey between 2018 and 2019.

Location	Year of survey	Method of Survey	Approx. area of surveys (m ²)	Species	Number of ind.	Mean Density (per m ²)	Mean Density (per 100 m ²)	Pooled Density (per 100 m ²)	Reference
Palawan Regions (El Nido)	1984-1985	Flowmeter	5,645	<i>Tc</i>	102	0.01807	1.81	4.48	Alcala, 1986
				<i>Tm</i>	144	0.02551	2.55		
				<i>Ts</i>	7	0.00124	0.12		
El Nido	1984-1986	Belt transects	25,500	<i>Hh</i>	12	0.00047	0.05	1.73	Junio et al., 1989
				<i>Hp</i>	1	0.00004	0.00		
				<i>Tc</i>	280	0.01098	1.10		
				<i>Tm</i>	23	0.00090	0.09		
				<i>Ts</i>	125	0.00490	0.49		
Cagayan Island	1984-1985	Flowmeter	21,000	<i>Tc</i>	6,901	0.32862	32.86	33.58	Alcala, 1986
				<i>Td</i>	8	0.00038	0.04		
				<i>Tm</i>	56	0.00267	0.27		
				<i>Ts</i>	57	0.00271	0.27		
				<i>Hh</i>	29	0.00138	0.14		
Cagayan Island, Palawan	1984-1986	Belt transects	6,400	<i>Tc</i>	33	0.00515	0.52	3.28	Junio et al., 1989
				<i>Hh</i>	5	0.00078	0.08		
				<i>Tm</i>	167	0.02609	2.61		
				<i>Tg</i>	1	0.00016	0.02		
				<i>Ts</i>	3	0.00047	0.05		
Cagayancillo (TRNP; Intertidal)	2005	Belt transects	300	<i>Tc</i>	40	1.33333	13.33	21.18	Dolorosa and Schoppe, 2005
<i>Hh</i>				10	0.03333	3.33			
Cagayancillo (TRNP; Shallow)			<i>Tc</i>	64	0.03048	3.05			
			<i>Tm</i>	27	0.01286	1.29			
Cagayancillo (TRNP; Deep)			<i>Ts</i>	2	0.00095	0.09			
Cagayancillo (TRNP)	2008	Belt transects	4,200	<i>Tc</i>	287	0.06833	6.83	8.36	Dolorosa and Jontila, 2012
				<i>Tm</i>	23	0.00548	0.55		

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				<i>Hp</i>	41	0.00976	0.98		
Cagayancillo Island	2015	Belt transects	2,000	<i>Tc</i>	6	0.00300	0.30	1.05	Dolorosa et al., 2015a
				<i>Tm</i>	14	0.00700	0.70		
				<i>Ts</i>	1	0.00050	0.05		
Aborlan (Sombrero Island)	1984-1986	Belt transects	2,000	<i>Hh</i>	1	0.00050	0.05	3.30	Junio et al., 1989
				<i>Tc</i>	50	0.02500	2.50		
				<i>Tm</i>	13	0.00650	0.65		
				<i>Ts</i>	2	0.00100	0.10		
Aborlan (Inagawan)	1984-1986	Belt transects	4,500	<i>Td</i>	1	0.00022	0.02	0.11	
				<i>Tm</i>	3	0.00067	0.07		
				<i>Ts</i>	1	0.00022	0.02		
Aborlan (Seven-lines)	2015	Belt transects	2,800	<i>Tc</i>	2	0.00071	0.07	0.14	Balisco et al., 2015
				<i>Ts</i>	2	0.00071	0.07		
Taytay (Camanga Pt., Binaluan Bay)	2002	Belt transects	1,200	<i>Tc</i>	25	0.02083	2.08	2.49	Sayson, 2003
<i>Ts</i>				3	0.00250	0.25			
<i>Tm</i>				1	0.00083	0.08			
<i>Hh</i>				1	0.00083	0.08			
Taytay (Lulukyon Pt., Binaluan Bay)			1,200	<i>Tc</i>	12	0.01000	1.00	1.58	
<i>Ts</i>				4	0.00333	0.33			
<i>Hh</i>				3	0.00250	0.25			
Taytay (Boat Rock, Binaluan Bay)			1,200	<i>Tc</i>	16	0.01333	1.33	1.58	
				<i>Ts</i>	2	0.00167	0.17		
				<i>Hh</i>	1	0.00083	0.08		
Taytay (Malapena Island, Binaluan Bay)			1,200	<i>Tc</i>	173	0.14417	14.42	14.84	
				<i>Ts</i>	5	0.00417	0.42		
Taytay (Taytay Bay)	2014	Belt transects	3,000	<i>Tc</i>	33	0.011	1.1	1.60	Dolorosa et al., 2014b
				<i>Tm</i>	5	0.0017	0.17		
				<i>Ts</i>	4	0.0013	0.13		

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				<i>Td</i>	3	0.001	0.10		
				<i>Hp</i>	3	0.001	0.10		
Taytay (Black Rock)	2019	Belt transects	1,000	<i>Tm</i>	31	0.03100	3.10	3.60	This study
				<i>Tc</i>	5	0.00500	0.50		
Roxas (Green Island)	2004	Belt transects	1,800	<i>Tc</i>	36	0.02	2.00	2.00	Condesa, 2005
Roxas (Caramay)			1,800	<i>Tc</i>	13	0.0072	0.72	0.72	
Roxas (Johnson Island)	2017	Belt transects	2,000	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	2	0.0010	0.10	0.10	Balisco et al., 2017a
Roxas (Green Island)			2,000	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	15	0.0075	0.75	0.75	
Roxas (Banwa/Puerco Island)	2018	Belt transects	750	<i>Ts</i>	5	0.00667	0.67	1.74	This study
				<i>Tc</i>	3	0.00400	0.40		
				<i>Tm</i>	2	0.00267	0.27		
				<i>Hh</i>	1	0.00133	0.13		
				<i>Hp</i>	2	0.00267	0.27		
PPC (Snake Island)	2004	Belt transect	4,800	<i>Tc</i>	580	0.12000	12.00	24.03	Bolen, 2005
				<i>Tm</i>	516	0.10000	10.00		
				<i>Ts</i>	70	0.02000	2.00		
				<i>Hh</i>	1	0.00030	0.03		
PPC (Honda Bay, Meara Island)	2004	Belt transect	200	<i>Td</i>	5	0.02500	2.50	9.50	Gonzales et al., 2014
<i>Tg</i>				3	0.01500	1.50			
<i>Ts</i>				11	0.05500	5.50			
PPC (Honda Bay, Sabang Reef Sanctuary)			200	<i>Td</i>	2	0.01000	1.00	2.50	
				<i>Ts</i>	3	0.01500	1.50		
PPC (St. Paul Rock)	2005	Belt transect	400	<i>Tc</i>	20	0.0500	5.00	10.00	Gonzales et al., 2005
				<i>Ts</i>	20	0.0500	5.00		
PPC (Martapi Reef, St. Paul Bay)				<i>Ts</i>	60	0.1500	15.00		
PPC (Honda Bay, Pandan Island)	2006	Belt transects	3,500	<i>Tc</i>	1	0.00029	0.03	0.57	Becira et al., 2012

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				<i>Ts</i>	17	0.00476	0.48		
				<i>Hp</i>	2	0.00057	0.06		
PPC (PPUR)	2007	Belt transect	942	<i>Tc</i>	122	0.129	12.90	20.23	Calinga, 2008
				<i>Tm</i>	47	0.049	4.99		
				<i>Hh</i>	22	0.023	2.34		
PPC (Honda Bay, Dos Palmas)	2009	Belt transect	400	<i>Tc</i>	2	0.00500	0.50	1.25	Dolorosa and Schoppe, 2010
				<i>Tm</i>	1	0.00250	0.25		
				<i>Ts</i>	2	0.00500	0.50		
PPC (Panglima Reef)	2017	Belt transect	500	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	2	0.00400	0.40	0.40	Balisco et al., 2017b
PPC (BMRS Reef, Binduyan)	2017	Belt transect	500	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	2	0.00400	0.40	0.40	
PPC (Lacson Reef)	2017	Belt transect	500	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	2	0.00400	0.40	0.40	
PPC (San Rafael Reef)	2017	Belt transect	500	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	1	0.00200	0.20	0.20	
PPC (Pungtod Elis Reef)	2017	Belt transect	500	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	8	0.01600	1.60	1.60	
PPC (Santos Reef)	2017	Belt transect	500	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	3	0.00200	0.20	0.20	
PPC (Binduyan)	2017	Belt transect	500	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	3	0.00600	0.60	0.60	
PPC (Binduyan)	2018	Belt transect	375	<i>Ts</i>	2	0.00530	0.53	0.53	
PPC (Binduyan)			750	<i>Tc</i>	1	0.00133	0.13	0.13	
Narra (Temple Island)	2015	Belt transects	4,400	<i>Ts</i>	1	0.00023	0.02	0.02	Dolorosa et al., 2015b
Narra (Rasa Island)	2015	Belt transects	4,000	<i>Tc</i>	5	0.00075	0.08	0.11	Dolorosa, 2016
				<i>Ts</i>	1	0.00025	0.03		
Narra (Rasa Island)	2016	Belt transects	3,600	<i>Tc</i>	13	0.00361	0.36	0.44	
				<i>Ts</i>	3	0.00083	0.08		

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Narra (Arena Island)	2017	Belt transects	1,200	<i>Tc</i>	4	0.00333	0.33	0.83	Sumandal, 2017
				<i>Td</i>	5	0.00417	0.42		
				<i>Hh</i>	1	0.00083	0.08		
Narra (Rasa Island)	2019	Belt transects	3,000	<i>Ts</i>	1	0.00033	0.03	0.06	This study
				<i>Tm</i>	1	0.00033	0.03		
Sofronio Española (Bessie Island)	2016	Belt transect	800	<i>Ts</i>	1	0.00125	0.13	0.13	Balisco et al., 2016
Sofronio Española	2017	Belt transects	3,000	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	6	0.00200	0.20	0.20	Balisco et al., 2017c
Kalayaan (Pag-asa Island)	2008	Belt transects	4,500	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	24	0.00530	0.53	0.53	Gonzales et al., 2008
Kalayaan (Pag-asa Island)	2016	Belt transects	4,000	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	209	0.05225	5.23	5.23	Gonzales, 2016
Brooke's Point (Mainit)	2017	Belt transects	1,500	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	4	0.00133	0.13	0.13	Balisco et al., 2017c
Bataraza (Sebentehan)	2017	Belt transects	1,000	<i>Tridacna</i> spp.	1	0.00100	0.10	0.10	Balisco et al., 2017c
Araceli (Hart Reef)	2019	Belt transects	750	<i>Tc</i>	13	0.01733	1.73	1.99	This study
				<i>Ts</i>	1	0.00133	0.13		
				<i>Tm</i>	1	0.00133	0.13		
San Vicente (Albague Island, Port Barton)	2018	Belt transects	1,125	<i>Ts</i>	1	0.00089	0.09	0.09	
San Vicente (Alvarez Island, Port Barton)			375	<i>Ts</i>	2	0.00533	0.53	0.53	
San Vicente (Capsalay Reef, Port Barton)	2019	Belt transects	750	<i>Ts</i>	1	0.00133	0.13	0.13	
San Vicente (Fantastic Reef, Port Barton)			1,500	<i>Ts</i>	4	0.00267	0.27	0.27	
			1,250	<i>Tc</i>	1	0.00080	0.08	0.32	

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San Vicente (Manta Ray Reef, Port Barton)				<i>Ts</i>	2	0.00160	0.16		
				<i>Tm</i>	1	0.00080	0.08		
San Vicente (Aquarium Reef, Port Barton)			750	<i>Tc</i>	8	0.01067	1.07	1.20	
				<i>Ts</i>	1	0.00133	0.13		